

A universal coral-specific ITS2 primer set for eDNA-based coral biodiversity monitoring

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Abstract

Monitoring coral diversity is critical for assessing biodiversity trajectories and understanding the impacts of environmental change on reef ecosystems. Environmental DNA (eDNA) has emerged as a powerful tool for non-invasive biodiversity assessments, enabling the detection of diverse taxa through molecular techniques. The ribosomal ITS2 region is well suited for coral diversity studies owing to its high interspecific and intraspecific variability, which supports fine-scale taxonomic discrimination. However, the effectiveness of eDNA-based approaches hinges on the development of primers that are both universal, enabling amplification across a broad range of coral taxa, and specific, thereby minimizing non-target amplification. Here, we present a novel coral-specific ITS2 primer set (amplicon size: ca. 450 bp) designed for PCR amplification and subsequent Illumina-sequencing of the ITS2 region. The primer set was tested across diverse coral and non-coral taxa to evaluate its performance in terms of specificity and universality. This study demonstrates the utility of the primer set for eDNA-based coral monitoring, warranting the development of a comprehensive coral ITS2 reference dataset to enable reliable detection of coral taxonomic signatures from eDNA, advancing biodiversity research and conservation in coral reef ecosystems.

Methods & Results

Universal coral ITS2 primers

The here-presented ITS2 primer set built on the available CoralITS2 and CoralITS2_acro primer pairs (Alexander et al., 2020; Brian et al., 2019; Dugal et al., 2022). An intermediate primer set, generated by modifying these primers to improve species recovery (modifications underlined: coral ITS2_for 5'-GADTCT TTG AAC GCA AAT GGC-3' and coral ITS2_rev 5'-TCG CCG TTA CTRRGG GAA TC-3'), achieved high amplification success but also exhibited substantial sponge co-amplification (data not shown), consistent with previous reports (Alexander et al., 2020; Dugal et al., 2022). To address this limitation, the primers were further refined by aligning coral ITS2 sequences from NCBI GenBank using MAFFT v7.526 (Kato et al., 2002), which motivated shifting the amplicon to a more coral-specific, restrictive locus (Figure 1). This refinement resulted in a triple-primer set—two forward and one reverse primers—that improved detection efficiency for scleractinian corals, while markedly reducing sponge-derived false positives (Table 1). The two forward primers are necessary to account for amplification of *Acropora* samples. NCBI Primer-BLAST (Ye et al., 2012) was used to assess broad amplification across coral species.

Figure 1. Overview of coral ITS2 alignment indicating primer target regions (left forward primers, right reverse primer in reverse complement orientation). The alignment file is available as fasta with this release and contains NCBI GenBank identifiers for easy retrieval of reference sequences (5' and 3' ends of sequences are trimmed in the provided alignment file).

Table 1. Universal coral-specific ITS2 primer set for eDNA-based coral diversity monitoring.

Primer name	Sequence	Tm [°C]	Annealing Temp. [°C]
coral_ITS2_eDNA_for	5'- CAA ATG GCG CTC TYG GG -3'	56-59°C	52°C
acro_ITS2_eDNA_for	5'- CAA ATG GCG CTC GTC TC -3'	56°C	52°C
coral_ITS2_eDNA_rev	5'- TCG CCG TTA CTR RGG GAA TC -3'	56°-62°C	52°C

Sample set & PCR amplification

DNA from 81 coral samples from the Red Sea served as a sample set for PCR trials, representing *Acropora*, *Astreopora*, *Echinopora*, *Favia*, *Favites*, *Galaxea*, *Goniastrea*, *Goniopora*, *Leptastrea*, *Lobophyllia*, *Montipora*, *Pavona*, *Platygyra*, *Pocillopora*, *Porites*, *Sarcophyton*, *Stylophora*, and unidentified genera. Coral colonies were photographed prior to sampling to allow visual taxonomic identification of coral host genera. Sampled specimens were stored in Ziploc plastic bags upon underwater collection and transported back to the shore in a cooler filled with seawater where they were transferred into 1.5 ml microcentrifuge tubes with DESS buffer (Voolstra et al., 2021, 2025), stored at -20°C until further processing. One liter of reef seawater was collected for each eDNA sample, transported to the shore in a cooler, and filtered using a 0.22 µm polyethersulfone filter. Filters were then transferred into 1.5 ml microcentrifuge tubes containing DESS buffer and stored at -20°C until further processing. DNA was extracted using the DNeasy Blood & Tissue kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany), followed by aDNA clean-up using the QIAquick PCR Purification Kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany) according to the manufacturer's guidelines. PCRs were conducted in a 10 µl reaction volume with the Qiagen Multiplex PCR kit using 5 µl 5x Master mix, 0.5 µM forward primer final concentration, 0.5 µM reverse primer final concentration, and 2 µl DNA template of a 1:10 dilution. Cycling conditions were: 95°C for 15 mins (hot start), followed by 30 cycles of 95°C for 30 secs, 52°C for 30 secs, 72°C for 30 secs, and a final extension at 72°C for 10 mins.

PCRs using the *coral_ITS2_eDNA_for* and *coral_ITS2_eDNA_rev* primer combination successfully amplified DNA from samples annotated as *Stylophora*, *Pocillopora*, *Pavona*, *Porites*, *Galaxea*, and *Platygyra*, and produced faint amplification products in all three eDNA samples (Figure 2A). However, no amplification was observed for *Acropora* or *Sarcophyton* (soft coral).

Amplified fragments were in the range of 400–600 bp, consistent with the expected size of the target amplicon region. PCR using the *acro ITS2_eDNA_for* and *coral ITS2_eDNA_rev* primer combination using eight additional samples, taxonomically identified as *Acropora*, successfully amplified DNA from seven samples and produced strong amplification products, while one sample (sample 43) showed only a faint band (Figure 2B).

Figure 2. Agarose gel electrophoresis of PCR products amplified from coral DNA and environmental DNA (eDNA). (A) Amplification using the *coral ITS2_eDNA_for* and *coral ITS2_eDNA_rev* primers on a subset of taxonomically annotated coral samples and individual eDNA water samples. (B) Amplification using the *acro ITS2_eDNA_for* and the *coral ITS2_eDNA_rev* primers on a subset of samples taxonomically identified as *Acropora*. L = DNA ladder (Genaxxon GenLadder 100 bp Plus 1.5 kbp). All PCRs were performed with an annealing temperature of 52 °C. Acr = *Acropora*, Sty = *Stylophora*, Poc = *Pocillopora*, Pav = *Pavona*, Por = *Porites*, Sar = *Sarcophyton*, Gal = *Galaxea*, Pla = *Platygyra*.

To evaluate primer performance across a broader range of coral taxa, PCRs were performed on the complete set of 81 coral samples. Using a 1:1 mixture of both forward primers resulted in successful amplification for the majority of samples with one prominent band and only four samples showing no detectable bands (Figure 3). The presence of more than one band in some samples is consistent with the co-amplification of fragments from both forward primers, as the fragment amplified by the *acro ITS2_eDNA_for* primer is slightly shorter than that amplified using the *coral ITS2_eDNA_for* primer. Increasing the annealing temperature from 52°C to 55°C did not improve this: more than one band was still observed in some samples, while others showed no detectable amplification at the higher annealing temperature (data not shown). Similarly, touchdown PCR with a stepwise decrease in annealing temperature from 65°C to 52°C in 1.3°C increments did not result in improved amplification (data not shown). DNA from *Symbiodiniaceae* culture samples produced weak amplification products at annealing temperatures of 52°C and 55°C, with the observed product size being around 300 bp (data not shown).

Figure 3. Agarose gel electrophoresis of PCR products amplified from coral DNA of *Acropora*, *Astreopora*, *Echinopora*, *Favia*, *Favites*, *Galaxea*, *Goniastrea*, *Goniopora*, *Leptastrea*, *Lobophyllia*, *Montipora*, *Pavona*, *Platygyra*, *Pocillopora*, *Porites*, *Sarcophyton*, *Stylophora*, and unidentified genera. Amplification using a 1:1 mixture of *coral ITS2_eDNA_for* and *acro ITS2_eDNA_for* forward primers on all 81 coral tissue samples. All PCRs were performed with an annealing temperature of 52°C. L = DNA ladder (Genaxxon GenLadder 100 bp Plus 1.5 kbp).

For the eDNA samples, amplification with the 1:1 mixture of both forward primers produced three bands of comparable intensity (Figure 4A), whereas amplification with the *coral ITS2_eDNA_for* primer alone produced two bands (Figure 4B). Sequencing of PCR products and subsequent analysis is ongoing and will clarify if all bands represent coral-amplified ITS2 DNA.

Figure 4. Agarose gel electrophoresis of PCR products amplified from environmental DNA (eDNA). (A) Amplification using a 1:1 mixture of *coral ITS2_eDNA_for* and *acro ITS2_eDNA_for* forward primers on 10 eDNA samples from seawater. (B) Amplification of the same sample set as in (A) using only the *coral ITS2_eDNA_for* forward primer. All PCRs were performed with an annealing temperature of 52°C. L = DNA ladder (Genaxxon GenLadder 100 bp Plus 1.5 kbp).

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Supplementary material

Alignment fasta file of ITS2 primers and coral ITS2 sequences with GenBank identifiers (sequences are trimmed; reverse primer is in reverse complement): coral ITS2 eDNA primers alignment.fasta

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